

"International Meditation Day: Harnessing Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation for Global Peace and Sustainable Well-Being"

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ABSTRACT:

Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation is a transformative, thought-driven practice that emphasises self-awareness, spiritual growth, and inner peace. Recognized globally for its potential to foster individual well-being and collective harmony, this practice aligns with the United Nations' International Meditation Day, highlighting its role in promoting sustainable peace. Raja Yoga stands out for its unique focus on soul consciousness and a personal connection with the Divine, offering a universal approach that transcends cultural and religious boundaries. Scientific research further supports its effectiveness in reducing stress, enhancing emotional regulation, improving cognitive functions, and promoting overall health. Through its cultivation of global peace, compassion, and ethical living, Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation offers a powerful strategy for creating a more peaceful and sustainable world.

KEYWORDS: Raja Yoga, Brahma Kumaris, Meditation, Inner peace, Spiritual growth, Global harmony

1. INTRODUCTION:

1.1 Advancing Inner Peace and Sustainable Well-Being through International Meditation Day

On December 6, 2024, the United Nations General Assembly declared December 21 as **World Meditation Day**, co-sponsored by India, Liechtenstein, Sri Lanka, and Mexico. This date aligns with the **Winter Solstice**, symbolising renewal, introspection, and spiritual enlightenment—values central to meditation and Indian traditions. India's leadership in advocating this resolution underscores its commitment to global wellness, previously demonstrated through initiatives like the **International Day of Yoga**, embodying its philosophy of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam* (the world is one family).

Meditation transcends cultural and religious boundaries, fostering mental well-being, stress relief, and societal harmony. In today's fast-paced world, this observance offers an opportunity for reflection and collective unity, addressing rising

mental health challenges and divisions. The solstice metaphorically reflects meditation's power to guide individuals from darkness to light, encouraging personal growth and collective renewal.

Organisations like the Brahma Kumaris play a vital role in expanding meditation's global reach through practices such as **Raj yoga Meditation**, offering free workshops and initiatives like **World Peace Meditation**. These efforts inspire individuals worldwide to cultivate inner peace, self-awareness, and emotional resilience. By adopting meditation, humanity can build **resilience**, **foster compassion**, and pave the way for sustainable global harmony. December 21, designated as **World Meditation Day**, stands as a powerful reminder to prioritise personal well-being and nurture collective peace in our interconnected world.

1.2 The Global Importance of Meditation

In an increasingly interconnected yet stress-laden world, individuals face mounting challenges, including mental health struggles, societal conflicts, and environmental crises. Meditation offers a proven antidote by calming the mind, enhancing self-awareness, and promoting mental clarity. It cultivates inner peace and emotional stability while fostering virtues like empathy and compassion—foundational qualities for building inclusive, harmonious societies.

Meditation transcends cultural and religious boundaries, uniting people in a shared pursuit of self-discovery and balance. By anchoring International Meditation Day in universal principles of peace and mindfulness, the UN provides an inclusive platform for individuals from diverse backgrounds to engage with meditation in ways that resonate with their personal and spiritual values.

1.3 Raja Yoga Meditation: A Path to Global Transformation

Among the many meditation practices, Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga stands out as a unique and impactful approach. Raja Yoga emphasises thought-based awareness and self-mastery, guiding individuals toward a deeper connection with spiritual truths and the cultivation of soul consciousness. It moves beyond rituals or physical postures, offering a universally accessible practice that integrates seamlessly into daily life.

Through its focus on virtues like patience, compassion, and resilience, Raja Yoga empowers individuals to overcome negativity and navigate life's challenges with clarity and purpose. While International Meditation Day provides a global

platform to promote the benefits of meditation broadly, the principles of Raja Yoga align closely with the UN's vision for sustainable peace and collective well-being. Featuring practices like Raja Yoga can further enrich the global discourse on meditation's role in fostering inner harmony and societal transformation.

1.4 Purpose of the Review

This review paper aims to highlight the global impact of meditation, focusing on Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation as a transformative practice for inner peace, resilience, and well-being. By exploring the UN's International Meditation Day and comparing Raja Yoga with other meditation techniques, the paper emphasizes its universal appeal and accessibility. Additionally, it underscores scientific research validating its mental, emotional, and spiritual benefits, encouraging a worldwide movement towards greater mindfulness, unity, and sustainable peace. Ultimately, it calls for collective action to embrace meditation for personal and global transformation.

1.5 Methodology

This review adopts an interdisciplinary approach to examine the global impact of Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation, emphasizing its role in promoting inner peace and sustainable well-being. The methodology combines insights from scholarly research, online blog posts, personal accounts, and other digital media. Sources include peer-reviewed journal articles, books, and reliable online platforms focused on the intersection of meditation, science, and spirituality. Comparative analysis with other meditation techniques, along with scientific studies validating Raja Yoga's benefits, informs the exploration. Despite potential biases in digital sources, the integration of diverse perspectives provides a well-rounded understanding of meditation's global appeal and impact.

2. RAJA YOGA MEDITATION IN THE GLOBAL CONTEXT

Meditation has long been celebrated as a transformative practice that transcends cultural and religious boundaries, fostering personal well-being and societal harmony. Across the globe, diverse traditions converge on a common aspiration: achieving mental clarity, emotional balance, and spiritual growth. The United Nations' recognition of International Meditation Day highlights meditation's universal relevance in addressing the challenges of modern life. Among these practices, Raja Yoga, particularly as taught by the Brahma Kumaris, stands out for its inclusivity and profound transformative potential, offering pathways to peace and enlightenment accessible to people of all faiths and backgrounds.

2.1 Global Meditation Practices: Diversity and Benefits

Meditation's universal appeal lies in its adaptability to various cultural, spiritual, and secular contexts. Key traditions include:

- **Mindfulness Meditation:** Rooted in Buddhism, mindfulness focuses on present-moment awareness and non-judgmental observation of thoughts and emotions. Popularized worldwide through practices like Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR), it has proven effective in reducing stress, anxiety, and depression while enhancing emotional resilience and mental clarity.
- **Mantra-Based Practices:** Found in Hindu traditions, mantra-based meditation involves chanting sacred phrases like "Om" to deepen concentration and spiritual awareness. Transcendental Meditation (TM), widely practiced across cultures, uses mantras to promote mental calmness and inner peace.
- **Modern Secular Techniques:** Adaptations like MBSR and TM have evolved to meet the needs of individuals seeking non-religious approaches to meditation. These methods address mental health challenges and chronic stress, making meditation accessible to people of all beliefs and lifestyles.
- **Vipassana Meditation:** One of Buddhism's oldest practices, Vipassana emphasises self-awareness through mindfulness of bodily sensations and thoughts. Practiced globally, it often involves silent retreats that provide profound insights into the impermanence of life and liberation from suffering.

2.2 Brahma Kumaris' Raja Yoga: A Path to Universal Inner Peace and Global Harmony

Raja Yoga offers a distinctive approach that resonates with individuals from diverse religious and cultural backgrounds. Unlike many practices, it focuses on the innate spiritual essence of the self, transcending dogma and ritual to foster a direct connection with the supreme soul (God). Raja Yoga emphasises mental discipline to overcome distractions, self-mastery to manage thoughts and emotions, and spiritual awakening to unlock inner peace and resilience. Its universal principles make it accessible to anyone, regardless of their faith or philosophical outlook, and its teachings emphasise unity, compassion, and global harmony.

2.3 Classical Foundations and Modern Relevance

The roots of Raja Yoga lie in the ancient wisdom of Patanjali's Yoga Sutras, which outline the eightfold path (Ashtanga Yoga) as a comprehensive guide to self-realisation. These principles are timeless, providing ethical and meditative practices that resonate across religions and cultures. Swami Vivekananda's efforts to introduce Raja Yoga to the West further broadened its appeal, emphasising mental discipline and divine connection as keys to spiritual fulfilment.

The Brahma Kumaris build on these foundations by presenting Raja Yoga in a modern, inclusive framework. Their focus on soul consciousness and universal values offers practical tools for integrating spirituality into everyday life. This approach transcends religious boundaries, encouraging practitioners to explore their inner potential and contribute to a more compassionate and harmonious world.

2.4 Meditation: A Global Path to Enlightenment

The diversity of meditation practices reflects humanity's shared quest for inner peace and spiritual fulfilment. Traditions like mindfulness, mantra-based meditation, and Vipassana offer profound benefits, yet Raja Yoga's universal principles and emphasis on divine connection make it uniquely transformative. By focusing on soul consciousness and the shared spiritual essence of all individuals, Raja Yoga fosters unity among people of different faiths and cultures.

In a world often divided by differences, Raja Yoga serves as a bridge to greater understanding, offering a timeless path to self-realisation and collective harmony. As meditation continues to gain global recognition, Raja Yoga stands out as a practice that not only empowers individuals but also inspires a vision of peace and enlightenment for all of humanity.

3. THE ESSENCE OF BRAHMA KUMARIS RAJA YOGA MEDITATION

Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation is a transformative practice that invites individuals from all cultures, backgrounds, and faiths to connect with their true selves and the divine. Known as the "Royal Yoga," it offers a path to self-awareness, spiritual awakening, and profound inner peace. What sets this practice apart is its simplicity and ability to integrate seamlessly into everyday life, making it accessible to anyone seeking a deeper connection to themselves and the world around them.

3.1 What is Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga?

At its core, Raja Yoga, as taught by the Brahma Kumaris, is a spiritual practice that emphasises self-mastery, inner awakening, and establishing a personal relationship with the divine. This meditation approach teaches that the self is not just a physical body but an eternal soul. Through Raja Yoga, practitioners connect with the Supreme Soul, the ultimate source of love, peace, and wisdom, to draw strength and spiritual energy for their everyday lives.

What makes Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga unique is its focus on a thought-driven approach to meditation. It is free from complicated rituals, mantras, and physical postures. Instead, it empowers practitioners to meditate with open eyes, allowing them to maintain a connection to their surroundings while experiencing inner peace. This makes it easy to incorporate into daily activities, whether at home, at work, or in social settings.

3.2 Key Principles of Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation

1. Thought-Driven Practice for Self-Awareness and Divine Connection:

Raja Yoga emphasises the power of thoughts in shaping our reality. By training the mind to focus on elevated thoughts aligned with spiritual principles, practitioners cultivate deeper self-awareness and a stronger connection with the divine. This shift in consciousness allows individuals to experience greater peace and clarity, enabling them to navigate life's challenges with grace.

2. Open-Eyed Meditation:

One of the defining aspects of Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga is its open-eyed meditation practice. Rather than retreating from the world, practitioners remain fully present and engaged with their surroundings while experiencing the inner peace and clarity gained from meditation. This practice encourages individuals to carry their meditative state into their daily lives, fostering peace, positivity, and mindfulness in every moment.

3. A Personal Relationship with the Divine:

Raja Yoga meditation fosters a deep, personal relationship with the Supreme Soul—the source of all spiritual energy. By focusing on this connection, practitioners are able to access an unending source of strength, love, and wisdom. This relationship empowers them to face challenges with resilience, transforming everyday difficulties into opportunities for growth and spiritual development.

4. Recognition of the Self as an Eternal Soul:

Central to Raja Yoga is the realisation that we are spiritual beings, not just physical bodies. This soul-conscious perspective shifts one's identity from material concerns to eternal truths, fostering a sense of detachment from external stressors and a deeper connection to lasting inner peace.

5. Absence of Rituals and Chants:

Unlike many meditation practices, Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga does not rely on rituals, physical postures, or chants. This simplicity makes it accessible to people from diverse cultures, traditions, and religious backgrounds. It transcends religious and cultural boundaries, offering a universal path to inner peace and spiritual growth.

3.3 The Impact of Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga

Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga empowers individuals to transform their inner world and, by extension, their external circumstances. It fosters:

- **Inner Peace:** Through a deep connection with the divine and the recognition of the self as an eternal soul, practitioners experience lasting tranquillity and mental clarity.

- **Spiritual Strength:** The relationship with the Supreme Soul provides an unlimited source of strength, enabling individuals to meet life's challenges with confidence and grace.
- **Universal Accessibility:** With its simplicity and universal principles, Raja Yoga transcends cultural and religious boundaries, offering a practical tool for spiritual transformation.

Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation is a simple yet profound practice that provides a direct pathway to self-realisation and spiritual empowerment. Its focus on thought-driven meditation, open-eyed practice, and the understanding of the self as an eternal soul makes it uniquely suited to modern life. Whether you are seeking peace, purpose, or spiritual growth, Raja Yoga offers a universal path that empowers individuals to create a more compassionate, harmonious, and peaceful world.

4. HOW BRAHMA KUMARIS RAJA YOGA DIFFERS FROM OTHER TECHNIQUES

A comparative analysis highlighting its simplicity and accessibility.

Meditation practices vary in approach, philosophy, and goals. While techniques like mindfulness, transcendental meditation (TM), and Vipassana primarily focus on awareness, stress relief, and personal insight, Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga sets itself apart with its emphasis on soul consciousness and a direct, personal connection to the Divine. Below is a comparative overview of Raja Yoga alongside other prominent meditation practices.

4.1 A Comparative Overview of Meditation Techniques

Aspect	Raja Yoga (Brahma Kumaris)	Mindfulness Meditation	Transcendental Meditation (TM)	Vipassana Meditation
Key Focus	Thought-based awareness, connection with the Supreme Soul.	Present-moment awareness and acceptance.	Repetition of a mantra for clarity.	Insight into mind-body connection.
Practice Style	Open-eyed, integrated into daily life.	Closed-eyed, formal or informal practice.	Closed-eyed, focused sessions.	Closed-eyed, intensive retreats.
Spiritual Orientation	Strongly spiritual, soul-consciousness, divine connection.	Secular, rooted in Buddhism.	Secular, rooted in Hindu traditions.	Spiritual, rooted in Buddhist teachings.
Primary Goal	Self-realisation, mental clarity, spiritual empowerment.	Stress reduction, emotional balance.	Stress relief, enhanced focus inner calm.	Liberation from suffering through insight.
Techniques Used	Visualisation, self-reflection, thought-based meditation.	Observation of thoughts and sensations.	Repetition of mantra.	Observation of sensations and thoughts.
Rituals/Mantras	None, focus on thoughts and self-awareness.	None, though adaptable to specific practices.	Yes, specific mantra repetition.	None, but often requires silence.
Accessibility	Universal, no physical postures or rituals required.	Highly accessible, minimal requirements.	Requires training for mantra initiation.	Often requires retreat settings.
Connection with the divine	Central to the practice, focuses on a personal bond with the Supreme Soul.	Not included, focus on personal awareness.	Indirect, may involve spiritual exploration.	Not emphasised, focuses on self-exploration.

4.2 Key Differences between Raja Yoga and Other Meditation Practices

1. **Open-Eyed vs. Closed-Eyed Practices:** Raja Yoga is practiced with open eyes, allowing individuals to remain engaged with the world while meditating. This contrasts with most techniques, which require closed eyes and a seated position, making Raja Yoga easier to incorporate into daily life.

2. **Divine Connection vs. Self-Awareness:** Raja Yoga emphasises a personal connection with the Supreme Soul, providing guidance, strength, and peace. In comparison, mindfulness, TM, and Vipassana generally focus on self-awareness, inner calm, and the understanding of personal thoughts and sensations, with little or no focus on a divine connection.
3. **Thought-Based Awareness vs. Silence or Mantras:** Raja Yoga engages practitioners' thoughts directly, emphasising the power of positive thinking to transform one's inner world. Unlike TM, which uses mantra repetition, or Vipassana, which involves silent observation, Raja Yoga's approach encourages active, purposeful thought and reflection.
4. **Secular vs. Spiritual Focus:** While techniques like mindfulness and TM are often taught in secular settings and appeal to modern lifestyles, Raja Yoga is deeply spiritual, focusing on the eternal nature of the soul and its relationship with the Divine. This makes it especially appealing to those seeking spiritual growth.

4.3 Why Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Stands Out

Raja Yoga's combination of thought-driven meditation, open-eyed practice, and emphasis on divine connection provides a unique path to spiritual and personal transformation. Compared to other techniques, it offers:

- **A Universal Approach:** Accessible to anyone without physical postures, rituals, or mantras.
- **Practical Integration:** Open-eyed meditation allows practitioners to maintain peace and clarity throughout their daily activities.
- **Spiritual Empowerment:** A direct relationship with the Supreme Soul offers boundless inner strength and peace.

While other practices provide valuable benefits, Raja Yoga's holistic approach makes it especially effective for those looking to balance spiritual growth with the practical demands of modern life.

5. UNIQUE STRENGTHS OF BRAHMA KUMARIS RAJA YOGA

5.1 Why is it ideal for individuals of all backgrounds and beliefs?

Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation offers a universally accessible and deeply transformative path that resonates across diverse cultures, religions, and lifestyles. This practice stands apart due to its simplicity, profound spiritual insights, and global community, making it suitable for anyone seeking inner peace, clarity, and personal growth. Here are some more key reasons why Raja Yoga is both unique and easy to adopt.

1. Direct Connection with the Supreme Soul

Raja Yoga emphasises establishing a direct personal relationship with the Supreme Soul, which serves as an endless source of peace, guidance, and spiritual energy. Unlike meditation practices that focus on abstract concepts, this direct connection empowers practitioners with a deeper sense of security and inner strength to navigate life's challenges.

2. No Complex Rituals or Physical Postures

Raja Yoga is accessible to individuals of all ages, physical abilities, and cultural backgrounds. There are no complicated physical postures or rituals to follow, making it easy for anyone to practice anytime, anywhere. This simplicity makes it ideal for people leading busy or dynamic lives, offering peace without requiring a change in lifestyle or special conditions.

3. Focus on Soul Consciousness

One of the core teachings of Raja Yoga is the recognition that we are eternal souls, not just physical beings. This soul-conscious perspective shifts attention away from material concerns and fosters a sense of lasting inner peace, self-awareness, and freedom from the distractions of the material world. It empowers individuals to find their true identity beyond physical limitations, encouraging a spiritual approach to everyday life.

4. Global Outreach and Universal Community

With centres in over 135 countries, Brahma Kumaris provides a global community where individuals from diverse backgrounds can come together to share in the practice of Raja Yoga. This worldwide network fosters unity and mutual respect, ensuring that no one, regardless of where they live, is excluded from the transformative benefits of Raja Yoga. The global accessibility of free courses and programs further supports this inclusivity.

5. Practical Integration into Modern Life

Raja Yoga is designed for integration into modern life, helping individuals maintain a meditative state throughout their daily activities. Open-eyed meditation allows practitioners to experience peace while engaging in work, travel, or social interactions, making it incredibly practical and adaptable. It doesn't require a special environment, making it easy to incorporate into both busy urban life and more peaceful rural settings.

6. Holistic Approach to Well-Being

Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga offers a holistic approach that nurtures mental, emotional, and spiritual well-being. It helps individuals develop emotional resilience, enhance mental clarity, and cultivate a calm, balanced mind. This all-encompassing practice allows practitioners to achieve peace and harmony not just within themselves, but also in their relationships and communities.

7. Inclusive for All Ages and Backgrounds

Raja Yoga does not require any prior experience, religious affiliation, or specific skills, making it open to everyone—children, adults, and the elderly alike. It also transcends cultural boundaries, making it a practice that people from any religious or non-religious background can adopt without feeling excluded. Its simplicity and adaptability make it a perfect choice for families, workplaces, and educational institutions seeking to promote peace and personal development.

8. Emphasizing Personal Responsibility and Karma

The concept of karma, which teaches that our actions influence our future, is a foundational element of Raja Yoga. It encourages mindful living, where individuals take responsibility for their thoughts and actions. This concept of cause and effect encourages ethical behaviour and promotes a conscious approach to life, fostering personal growth and contributing to the well-being of others and society.

9. A Gateway to Global Peace

Brahma Kumaris advocates that personal transformation through Raja Yoga contributes to creating a peaceful world. By focusing on cultivating virtues such as kindness, compassion, and positive thinking, individuals can help heal social divisions, resolve conflicts, and promote understanding across cultures. The ripple effect of peaceful individuals can lead to collective societal healing and harmony, making Raja Yoga a tool for global peace.

10. Empowers Social and Environmental Responsibility

Raja Yoga also inspires practitioners to become more responsible in their social and environmental interactions. As individuals cultivate a deeper sense of inner peace, they tend to make decisions that are more conscious of the environment and others' well-being. This practice helps to foster a greater sense of connection with the planet and encourages mindful consumption, supporting a more sustainable and compassionate world.

11. Access to Ongoing Support and Learning

The Brahma Kumaris centres provide continuous opportunities for learning and growth. From in-person workshops to online resources, practitioners can access ongoing support to deepen their practice and understanding. This availability of resources ensures that individuals can continue to evolve spiritually, fostering a lifelong journey of personal growth.

12. Universal Accessibility for All Individuals

Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation is open to everyone, regardless of formal education, caste, religion, nationality, gender, age, or cultural background. The practice does not require any prior knowledge or special skills, making it incredibly inclusive. Whether you are a student, a working professional, or someone in retirement, Raja Yoga can be easily adopted by anyone, at any stage of life. This universal accessibility ensures that all individuals—no matter their circumstances—can benefit from its transformative teachings. It is a practice that transcends all boundaries, offering a path to inner peace, personal growth, and spiritual fulfilment for people from all walks of life.

5.2 Personal, Global, and Environmental Benefits of Adopting Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation

a) Personal Benefits:

- 1. Inner Peace and Emotional Balance:** Raja Yoga fosters inner peace and emotional stability, helping practitioners stay calm and balanced in the face of life's challenges.
- 2. Self-Awareness and Personal Growth:** Through self-reflection, Raja Yoga promotes greater self-awareness, leading to personal growth and more intentional life choices.
- 3. Enhanced Mental Clarity and Focus:** The practice clears mental clutter, improving focus, decision-making, and overall mental clarity.

4. **Improved Relationships:** Raja Yoga cultivates love, patience, and empathy, enhancing communication and creating healthier, more harmonious relationships.
5. **Increased Resilience:** It strengthens emotional resilience, helping individuals cope with adversity and change with grace and confidence.
6. **Spiritual Empowerment:** The direct connection with the Supreme Soul enhances spiritual strength, providing purpose and fulfillment.

b) Environmental Benefits:

1. **Promoting Eco-Consciousness:** The emphasis on soul-consciousness and self-awareness nurtures a deep respect for nature and the environment, encouraging more eco-friendly behaviors.
2. **Mindful Consumption:** Raja Yoga encourages mindfulness in all aspects of life, including consumption. Practitioners are more likely to make choices that are sustainable and aligned with environmental well-being.
3. **Fostering a Connection with Nature:** The practice's focus on connecting with the divine and the soul can deepen individuals' appreciation for the natural world, motivating actions to protect it.
4. **Encouraging Simple Living:** Through self-awareness and detachment from material desires, Raja Yoga promotes a simpler lifestyle, which can lead to reduced waste and a smaller environmental footprint.
5. **Environmental Harmony:** The spiritual principles of peace and balance that guide Raja Yoga align with the values of environmental sustainability, creating a world where humans live in harmony with nature.

c) Global Benefits:

1. **Fostering Global Peace:** By promoting inner peace, Raja Yoga creates a ripple effect, encouraging harmony and reducing conflict at the global level.
2. **Promoting Tolerance and Unity:** The practice unites individuals across cultural and religious boundaries, fostering global unity and understanding.
3. **Encouraging Ethical Living:** Raja Yoga teaches the principle of karma, inspiring responsible actions that benefit society and the planet.
4. **Global Health and Well-Being:** Reduced stress and emotional resilience improve overall health, contributing to healthier communities worldwide.
5. **Sustainable Living:** Raja Yoga promotes mindfulness and conscious living, encouraging sustainable practices that protect the environment.
6. **Building a supportive community:** The global Brahma Kumaris network provides a sense of community, offering spiritual support and shared learning across borders.

By adopting Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga, individuals experience personal transformation, contribute to global unity and sustainability, and promote environmental consciousness. This practice not only enhances individual well-being but also nurtures a more peaceful, ethical, and eco-conscious world.

6. THE SCIENTIFIC BACKING OF BRAHMA KUMARIS RAJA YOGA MEDITATION

Scientific research increasingly validates the profound impact of meditation on mental, emotional, and physical well-being. Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga, with its unique emphasis on soul consciousness, thought-based awareness, and connection with the Divine, has garnered significant attention. Below are some key findings from global research that highlight the effectiveness of Raja Yoga in enhancing health, education, and well-being.

A. Stress Reduction and Emotional Regulation

- **Cortisol Reduction:** Studies show that Raja Yoga meditation helps reduce cortisol, the body's primary stress hormone. Lower cortisol levels contribute to reduced anxiety and a more relaxed state.
- **Emotional Stability:** Practitioners report greater emotional balance and resilience. Research indicates increased brain activity in the prefrontal cortex, which is associated with emotional regulation and self-control.
- **Psychological Resilience:** Raja Yoga has been shown to improve the ability to cope with stress and adversity, promoting greater mental resilience.

B. Cognitive Benefits: Focus, Clarity, and Mental Agility

- **Improved Focus:** Meditation enhances brain functions related to concentration and cognitive control, leading to better focus. Studies show that consistent meditation improves attention span, making it easier to stay engaged in academic or professional tasks.
- **Increased Mental Clarity:** Raja Yoga promotes mental stillness, improving decision-making, problem-solving, and thought clarity, even in stressful situations.
- **Neuroplasticity:** Functional MRI studies show that long-term meditation increases grey matter density in brain areas related to memory, decision-making, and emotional regulation.

C. Positive Impact on Education

- **Enhanced Learning Capacity:** Research has shown that meditation practices, including Raja Yoga, improve the ability to absorb and retain information. Meditation fosters an enhanced state of focus and mental clarity, which can help students perform better academically.
- **Improved Memory and Retention:** Meditation practices such as Raja Yoga have been linked to improved memory, which is essential for academic success. Studies suggest that meditation strengthens the hippocampus, the brain region associated with memory formation.

- **Reduction in Test Anxiety:** Many students experience stress and anxiety during exams. Raja Yoga helps manage such stress, improving performance by promoting calmness and focus before and during tests.

D. Brainwave Activity and Neurophysiological Changes

- **EEG Brainwave Studies:** Electroencephalogram (EEG) studies have revealed increased alpha and theta brainwave activity among Raja Yoga practitioners. These brainwaves are associated with relaxation, mental clarity, and heightened creativity.
- **Meditative States:** Raja Yoga induces deep relaxation and focused attention, allowing practitioners to enter states of heightened awareness and clarity.

E. Emotional Health and Well-being

- **Increased Compassion and Empathy:** Regular practitioners of Raja Yoga exhibit higher levels of compassion and empathy, with research showing enhanced neural circuits linked to prosocial behaviors.
- **Self-Worth and Identity:** Raja Yoga fosters a sense of self-worth by helping individuals recognize their eternal soul, distinct from the body. This contributes to improved self-esteem and emotional resilience.
- **Reduction in Negative Emotions:** Meditation in Raja Yoga has been shown to reduce negative emotional states such as anxiety and depression, promoting greater emotional stability.

F. Case Study: Raja Yoga and Brain Function Improvement

- **Prefrontal Cortex Activation:** A study found that Raja Yoga practitioners showed increased activity in the prefrontal cortex, responsible for decision-making and emotional control. This suggests improved cognitive function and emotional regulation.
- **Emotional Balance:** Regular practitioners of Raja Yoga exhibited less reactivity to stress and demonstrated greater emotional stability, likely due to the practice's focus on soul consciousness and inner peace.

G. Broader Health Impacts of Raja Yoga

- **Lower Blood Pressure:** Raja Yoga meditation has been shown to help lower blood pressure by promoting relaxation and reducing stress levels.
- **Improved Immune Function:** Meditation enhances immune function by reducing stress, which plays a role in maintaining physical health.
- **Reduced Risk of Chronic Disease:** Research suggests that regular meditation, including Raja Yoga, can lower the risk of chronic illnesses like heart disease and diabetes, due to its stress-reducing and health-enhancing effects.

7. A CALL TO EMBRACE INNER PEACE: GLOBAL IMPACT OF BRAHMA KUMARIS RAJA YOGA

In a world filled with stress, uncertainty, and division, the search for inner peace has become increasingly important. Meditation has long been recognised as a transformative tool for fostering emotional balance, mental clarity, and spiritual growth. Among various meditation practices, Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation stands out as a universal approach, offering a pathway to personal well-being and global harmony.

7.1 Meditation: A Universal Path to Harmony

Meditation is more than just an individual practice—it has the potential to positively impact families, communities, and entire societies. While many meditation techniques like mindfulness, Vipassana, and mantra-based practices offer benefits such as stress relief and enhanced focus, Raja Yoga meditation is distinct in its simplicity and depth. It provides a holistic approach that blends self-awareness, spiritual wisdom, and practical application in everyday life.

Raja Yoga: Connecting Mind, Spirit, and Daily Life

Raja Yoga offers a universal method that anyone can practice, regardless of their culture, religion, or background. What sets it apart is its focus on thought-based awareness, helping practitioners connect with their true self and with the Divine, which brings lasting peace and purpose. Raja Yoga teaches individuals to:

1. **Recognize their true identity as eternal souls**, separate from the physical body, fostering a sense of inner strength and resilience.
2. **Re-establish a connection with the Supreme Soul**, a source of peace, love, and guidance, empowering individuals to live with purpose.
3. **Apply meditative awareness in daily life**, transforming everyday challenges into opportunities for growth, service, and peace.

This practice doesn't require physical postures or rituals, making it accessible to everyone, irrespective of their lifestyle or beliefs.

7.2 A Message of Unity and Hope

The teachings of Raja Yoga carry a powerful message of unity, emphasising that personal transformation is key to creating global harmony. As more people around the world adopt this meditation practice, a collective shift toward peace, empathy, and mutual respect is possible. Raja Yoga highlights the interconnectedness of all beings and the transformative power of elevated thoughts.

As individuals embrace this practice, they not only experience personal growth but also contribute to a more peaceful, compassionate world. This ripple effect illustrates that societal progress begins with the cultivation of inner peace.

7.3 A Call to Action

In a time when technological advancements and global challenges shape our world, there is an urgent need for greater focus on mental and spiritual well-being. Raja Yoga provides a simple, accessible, and profound solution for people from all walks of life, regardless of their background or beliefs.

By fostering inner peace, we have the power to create a harmonious future for all. Let this be a call to action: to look within, embrace the transformative power of Raja Yoga meditation, and help build a world united in love, understanding, and peace. Together, through the practice of meditation, we can spark hope and make a lasting difference—one peaceful mind at a time.

8. CONCLUSION

Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation offers a ground breaking yet universally accessible pathway to personal and collective transformation, making it a vital strategy in advancing the goals of International Meditation Day. Recognised for its profound ability to foster inner peace and sustainable well-being, Raja Yoga directly addresses the growing global need for resilience, mindfulness, and harmony in an era defined by stress, uncertainty, and division.

This unique practice, endorsed for its emphasis on soul consciousness and a direct connection with the Divine, transcends cultural, religious, and social barriers. Its simplicity and integration into daily life enable individuals from all walks of life to experience the benefits of reduced stress, enhanced emotional balance, improved mental clarity, and holistic health. Scientific research supports these transformative outcomes, underscoring Raja Yoga's role in fostering psychological, emotional, and physical well-being.

Beyond personal growth, Raja Yoga serves as a catalyst for societal progress, nurturing virtues such as empathy, compassion, and ethical responsibility. By empowering individuals to embody peace and live sustainably, it contributes meaningfully to global efforts to achieve unity, cooperation, and ecological balance. Raja Yoga offers a compelling vision for how inner transformation can inspire collective action, bridging divides and fostering a shared sense of purpose for humanity.

In a world increasingly in need of innovative and inclusive solutions, Raja Yoga emerges as a beacon of hope. Its alignment with the principles of the United Nations—peace, equality, and sustainability—positions it as an indispensable tool for addressing contemporary challenges. By embracing Raja Yoga, individuals and nations alike can contribute to a global culture of peace and harmony, ensuring a more sustainable and compassionate future for all.

9. CONFLICT OF INTEREST : Nil

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12. REFERENCES

- [1]A., R., S, S., & D, L. (2022). Meditation: a saviour for balancing the autonomic functions. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/dc176046113012bd34da5086c05625415043db9b>
- [2]Aalasyam, Naveen & Sayeli, Vijaykumar & Pokala, Uma & Praveen, Kamatham & Goothy, Sai Sailesh. (2022). Effectiveness of 12 Weeks of Practice of Raja Yoga Meditation on Cognitive Functions in Young Adults. *INTRODUCTIONS. Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*. 18. 2022. 10.47750/pnr.2022.13.S08.586
- [3]Adhikari, Kishor. (2012). Study of Effect of Vipassana on Anxiety and Depression. *International Journal of Psychology and Behavioral Sciences*. 2012. 274-276. 10.5923/j.ijpbs.20120206.11, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233987152_Study_of_Effect_of_Vipassana_on_Anxiety_and_Depression
- [4]Agarwal, J.L., Singh, A.K., & Aggarwal, G. (2015). Effect of Rajayoga Meditation on Blood Pressure, Heart Rate, Cardiac Output, Cardiac Index, Peripheral Blood Flow (Right Upper Limb & Lower Limb). *International Journal of Physiology*, 3, 151-156.
- [5]Al-Hussaini, A., Dorvlo, A. S., Antony, S. X., Chavan, D., Dave, J., Purecha, V., Al-Rahbi, S., & Al-Adawi, S. (2001). Vipassana meditation: A naturalistic, preliminary observation in Muscat. *Journal for scientific research. Medical sciences*, 3(2), 87–92.

- [6] Araújo, R. V., Fernandes, A. F. C., Campelo, R. C. V., Silva, R. A., & Nery, I. S. (2021). Effect of Raja Yoga Meditation on the Distress and Anxiety Levels of Women with Breast Cancer. *Religions*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel12080590>
- [7] Aristotle on the soul. (2016). University of Washington. <https://faculty.washington.edu/smcohen/320/psyche.htm>
- [8] Arora, S., Singh, G., & Dhyani, M. (2022). Impact of Brahma Kumari's Raja Yoga meditation on quality of life of patients with alcohol use disorder: A quasi-experimental study. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(12), 2452–2457, [file:///C:/Users/Nagesh/Downloads/JPSP+-+2022+-+190%20\(1\).pdf](file:///C:/Users/Nagesh/Downloads/JPSP+-+2022+-+190%20(1).pdf)
- [9] At United Nations, Brahma Kumaris, <https://www.brahmakumaris.com/services-outreach/at-united-nation/>
- [10] Atla, Srinivas & Reddy, & Oraganti, Swapna. (2024). The Role of Raj yoga Meditation in Stress Management Among Deaf Secondary School Students A Review. 10.13140/RG.2.2.17738.38081, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/383303923_The_Role_of_Raj_yoga_Meditation_in_Stress_Management_Among_Deaf_Secondary_School_Students_A_Review
- [11] Atman Soul, Self & Brahman. (1998). Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/atman>
- [12] Babu, M. G. R., Kadavigere, R., Koteswara, P., Sathian, B., & Rai, K. S. (2020). Rajyoga meditation induces grey matter volume changes in regions that process reward and happiness. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-73221-x>
- [13] Barnes, V. A., Treiber, F. A., & Davis, H. (2001). Impact of Transcendental Meditation on cardiovascular function at rest and during acute stress in adolescents with high normal blood pressure. *Journal of psychosomatic research*, 51(4), 597–605. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3999\(01\)00261-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-3999(01)00261-6)
- [14] Bharshankar, J. R., Mandape, A. D., Phatak, M. S., & Bharshankar, R. N. (2015). Autonomic Functions In Raja-yoga Meditators. *Indian journal of physiology and pharmacology*, 59(4), 396–401.
- [15] BK Shivani, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/BK_Shivani
- [16] BKWSU, UN World Meditation day with Sister Jayanti, <https://gch.brahmakumaris.uk/whatson-full/singleevent/6418445>
- [17] BKWSU, https://www.newworldencyclopedia.org/entry/Brahma_Kumaris_World_Spiritual_University
- [18] Brahma Kumaris at the United Nations, <https://un.brahmakumaris.org/>
- [19] Brahma Kumaris- Home, <https://www.brahmakumaris.org/>
- [20] Brahma Kumaris- Introduction, <https://www.brahmakumaris.org/about-us/introduction>
- [21] Brahma kumaris- Our History- <https://brahmakumaris.gr/bk/en/our-history/>
- [22] Brahma Kumaris Singapore. (n.d.), <https://brahmakumaris.org.sg/meditation/>
- [23] Brahma Kumaris Wikipedia.", https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brahma_Kumaris
- [24] Brahma Kumaris World Spiritual University (BKWSU) - CDAMM. (2024). CDAMM. <https://www.cdamm.org/articles/brahma-kumaris>
- [25] Brahma Kumaris world spiritual University, https://www.newworldencyclopedia.org/entry/Brahma_Kumaris_World_Spiritual_University
- [26] Brahma Kumaris world spiritual University, Religion-WIKI, https://religion.fandom.com/wiki/Brahma_Kumaris_World_Spiritual_University
- [27] Brahma Kumaris world spiritual University, Wikipedia Audio, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=09OLNLak4JU>
- [28] Brahma Kumaris(@brahma kumaris), <https://www.instagram.com/brahmakumaris/?hl=en>
- [29] Brahma Kumaris, A Treasure of Knowledge, You Tube, <https://www.youtube.com/@brahmakumarisatresureofkn4457>
- [30] Brahma Kumaris, https://citizendium.org/wiki/Brahma_Kumaris
- [31] BRAHMA KUMARIS, HTTPS://EN.DHARMAPEDIA.NET/WIKI/BRAHMA_KUMARIS
- [32] Brahma Kumaris, https://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brahma_Kumaris
- [33] Brahma Kumaris, <https://www.brahmakumaris.com/>
- [34] Brahma Kumaris. (2018). Benefits of meditation. <https://bk.ooo/benefits-of-meditation/>
- [35] Brahma Kumaris. (2024). Brahma Kumaris – Experiments, <http://iweb-dev.bkwsu.eu/wisdom/god-knows/experiments>
- [36] Brahma Kumaris. (2024). Brahma Kumaris - Experiments. Brahma Kumaris. <http://iweb-dev.bkwsu.eu/wisdom/god-knows/experiments>
- [37] Brahma Kumaris. (2024). Brahma Kumaris: A different consciousness. <https://www.brahmakumaris.org/hope/environment/a-different-consciousness>
- [38] Brahma Kumaris. (2024). Reflecting on the self in the mirror of silence. Brahma Kumaris. <https://www.brahmakumaris.org/>
- [39] Brahma Kumaris. (2024). Soul » Who am I? Brahma Kumaris. <https://www.shivbabas.org/who-am-i-the-soul>
- [40] Brahma Kumaris. (2024). Soul consciousness – The Brahma Kumaris. Australia. <https://brahmakumaris.org.au/new/soul-consciousness/>
- [41] Brahma Kumaris. (2024). Soul. Brahma Kumaris. <https://www.brahmakumaris.org/wisdom/soul>
- [42] Brahma Kumaris. (2024). Introduction, <https://www.brahmakumaris.org/about-us/introduction>
- [43] Breedvelt, J., Amanvermez, Y., Harrer, M., Karyotaki, E., Gilbody, S., Bockting, C., Cuijpers, P., & Ebert, D. (2019). The Effects of Meditation, Yoga, and Mindfulness on Depression, Anxiety, and Stress in Tertiary

- Education Students: A Meta-Analysis. Frontiers in Psychiatry. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsy.2019.00193/full>
- [44]Calderone, A., Latella, D., Impellizzeri, F., de Pasquale, P., Famà, F., Quartarone, A., & Calabrò, R. S. (2024). Neurobiological Changes Induced by Mindfulness and Meditation: A Systematic Review. *Biomedicines*, 12(11), 2613. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines12112613>
- [45]Chalageri, E., Vishwakarma, G., Ranjan, R. L., Govindaraj, R., & Chhabra, H. S. (2021). Effect of Rāja yoga Meditation on Psychological and Functional Outcomes in Spinal Cord Injury Patients. *International journal of yoga*, 14(1), 36–42. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijoy.IJOY_68_20
- [46]Chalageri, E., Vishwakarma, G., Ranjan, R., Govindaraj, R., & Chhabra, H. (2021). Effect of Rāja yoga Meditation on Psychological and Functional Outcomes in Spinal Cord Injury Patients. *International Journal of Yoga*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/7f34a1a4608c29a0d99cf61724b4f30de1fa8108>
- [47]CIVILS DAILY, UNGA DECLARES DECEMBER 21 AS WORLD MEDITATION DAY, <HTTPS://WWW.CIVILSDAILY.COM/NEWS/UNGA-DECLARES-DECEMBER-21-AS-WORLD-MEDITATIONDAY/#:~:TEXT=ABOUT%20THE%20WORLD%20MEDITATION%20DAY,DATE%20FOR%20THIS%20ANNUAL%20OBSERVANCE>.
- [48]Contributors to Wikimedia projects. (2024). Brahma Kumaris. In Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Brahma_Kumaris
- [49]Doowa, A. K. (2021). Effect of Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga meditation for increasing happiness and life satisfaction overall health & wellness: Case study in Thailand (Doctoral dissertation, Yoga-Samskrutham University, Florida, USA). Human Resource Development Institute of Thailand.
- [50]Dr. Nagesh NV. (2024). Bhavishya Malika's Divine Prophecies and Brahma Kumaris' Teachings: Unveiling the Secret to Unprecedented Global Transformation. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 11(12), b564–b574. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14360824>, Retrieved from <http://www.jetir.org/view?paper=JETIR2412153>
- [51]Dr. Nagesh NV. (2024). The Science of the Soul: A Multidisciplinary Exploration. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 11(12), b540–b553. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14360260>, Retrieved from <https://www.jetir.org/view?paper=JETIR2412150>
- [52]Existence of GOD, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Existence_of_God
- [53]Experiments with Peace and Disarmament, BKWSU, <https://un.brahmakumaris.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/2009-Experiments-in-Values-peace1.pdf?dl=1>
- [54]Experiments with values, <https://un.brahmakumaris.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/2009-Experiments-in-Values-overview1.pdf?dl=1>
- [55]FAQ's, Brahma Kumaris, <https://www.brahmakumaris.org/about-us/faqs>
- [56]FAQ's, Brahma Kumaris, <https://www.brahmakumaris.com/soul-sustenance/purifying-the-soul-with-rajyoga-meditation/>
- [57]Gayatri, S. (2019). a study on the impact of brahma kumaris raja yoga meditation and mindfulness based cognitive therapy on the emotional intelligence of adolescent in chennai city. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/0e7bbdfb274bb59e4796a6fca3e5e85df919328f>
- [58]Global CoOperation House, UK, <https://www.instagram.com/globalcooperationhouse/p/DDpfueHOiKJ/>
- [59]God is one for all, Brahma Kumaris, <https://www.brahmakumaris.org/wisdom/god-knows/god-is-one-for-all>
- [60]Gu, Q., Hou, J.-C., & Fang, X. (2018). Mindfulness Meditation for Primary Headache Pain: A Meta-Analysis. *Chinese Medical Journal*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/66f298c0f96601762f2cc3b2941f6adc9a2e3a94>
- [61]Gupta, D.K. (2022). Raj Yoga Meditation as a Pivotal pillar of Holistic Health-Mini Review, <IJCRT2205722.pdf>
- [62]Gupta, K., & Indu. (2022). Raj Yoga meditation as a pivotal pillar of holistic health: Mini review. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 10(5), g230–g239. Retrieved from <https://ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2205722.pdf>
- [63]Gupta, M., Jain, S., & Kumar, V. (2016). Effect of Raja Yoga Meditation on Pulmonary Functions of Young Obese Medical Students. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development*, 7, 1-4, <indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:ijphrd&volume=7&issue=2&article=001>,
- [64]Gupta, M., Kumar, V., & Agarwal, J. (2014). Effect of rajayoga meditation of brahma kumaris on pulmonary functions. <https://www.indianjournals.com/ijor.aspx?target=ijor:ijp2&volume=2&issue=2&article=006>
- [65]Gupta, N., Arora, J., Dixit, R., Garg, S. J., & Agarwal, J. (2023). EEG patterns in long-term Brahmakumari meditators and their possible significance. *National Journal of Physiology, Pharmacy and Pharmacology*. https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/0ac28b13d024396ba4ff7865dfdeb6d8e9d1bdd3,CR:SP:ATAO:TX_1~ABS:AT/CR:SP:TX_2~ABS:AT
- [66]HEALTHLINE, THE BENEFITS OF VIPASSANA MEDITATION AND HOW TO GET STARTED, <HTTPS://WWW.HEALTHLINE.COM/HEALTH/VIPASSANA-MEDITATION>
- [67]Hofmann, S.G., Sawyer, A.T., Witt, A.A., & Oh, D. (2010). The effect of mindfulness-based therapy on anxiety and depression: A meta-analytic review. *Journal of consulting and clinical psychology*, 78 2, 169-83.
- [68]How to meditate? <https://www.brahmakumaris.org/meditation/how-to-meditate> <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/26f4ce4154c0375fa7edea243afaa3a0ddea463e>
- [69]Is there any scientific evidence about the existence of the human soul? (2024). Quora. <https://www.quora.com/Is-there-any-scientific-evidence-about-the-existence-of-the-human-soul>

- [70]Jaiswal, S. (2024). Exploring Emotional Intelligence and Stress: A Comparative Analysis of Raja Yoga Meditation Practitioners and Non-Practitioners. *African Journal of Biomedical Research*. <https://doi.org/10.53555/ajbr.v27i4s.4535>
- [71]Jaiswal, Simran. (2024). Exploring Emotional Intelligence and Stress: A Comparative Analysis of Raja Yoga Meditation Practitioners and Non-Practitioners. *African Journal of Biomedical Research*. 27. 5031-5036. 10.53555/AJBR.v27i4S.4535, DOI: [10.53555/AJBR.v27i4S.4535](https://doi.org/10.53555/AJBR.v27i4S.4535)
- [72]Joshi, S. P., Wong, A. I., Brucker, A., Ardito, T. A., Chow, S. C., Vaishnavi, S., & Lee, P. J. (2022). Efficacy of Transcendental Meditation to Reduce Stress Among Health Care Workers: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA network open*, 5(9), e2231917. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2022.31917>
- [73]Journey and History, Braham Kumaris, <https://www.brahmakumaris.com/journey/>
- [74]Karmakar, D., Devi, B., & Nath, B. D. (2017). Rejuvenating life through spirituality: Role of Rajyoga. *International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field*, 3(8), 202–207. Available online at <https://www.ijirmf.com/wp-content/uploads/IJIRMF201708036.pdf>
- [75]Kaur, H. (2011). Effect of Rajyoga Meditation on the Heart Rate, Blood Pressure and ECG, <https://www.jcdr.net/articles/pdf/1780/6%20-%203406.pdf>.
- [76]Khanal, M. K., Karimi, L., Saunders, P., Schneider, R. H., Salerno, J., Livesay, K., Hallam, K. T., & de Courten, B. (2024). The promising role of Transcendental Meditation in the prevention and treatment of cardiometabolic diseases: A systematic review. *Obesity Reviews*, 25(10), e13800. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.13800>
- [77]Kiran, Chalana, H., Arora, A.K., & Girgila, K. (2014). EFFECT OF SHORT TERM RAJYOGA MEDITATION ON ANXIETY AND DEPRESSION, [Kiran.pdf](https://www.ijirmf.com/wp-content/uploads/IJIRMF201708036.pdf)
- [78]Kiran, Girgila, K. K., Chalana, H., & Singh, H. (2014). Effect of rajyoga meditation on chronic tension headache. *Indian journal of physiology and pharmacology*, 58(2), 157–161.
- [79]Kiran, H. C., Arora, A. K., & Girgila, K. K. (2014). Effect of short-term Rajyoga meditation on anxiety and depression. *Pakistan Journal of Physiology*, 10(1–2), 18–20. Retrieved from <https://www.pps.org.pk/PJP/10-1/Kiran.pdf>
- [80]Kiran, U., Ladha, S., Makhija, N., Kapoor, P., Choudhury, M., Das, S., Gharde, P., Malik, V., & Airan, B. (2017). The role of Rajyoga meditation for modulation of anxiety and serum cortisol in patients undergoing coronary artery bypass surgery: A prospective randomized control study. *Annals of Cardiac Anaesthesia*. https://doi.org/10.4103/aca.aca_32_17
- [81]Knowledge - Brahma Kumaris, <https://brahmakumarisresearch.org/knowledge>
- [82]Kora, P., Rajani, A., Chinnaiyah, M. C., Madhavi, K. R., Swaraja, K., & Meenakshi, K. (2021). EEG-Based Brain-Electric Activity Detection During Meditation Using Spectral Estimation Techniques. *Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/457463d309d4b62f8062f3520e861e7681cd8fe3>
- [83]Kumar, P., & Singh, S. (2024). Health benefits of Vipassana meditation: A comprehensive review. *Indian Journal of Positive Psychology*, 15(1), 55–58. Retrieved from <https://iahrw.org/our-services/journals/indian-journal-of-positive-psychology/>
- [84]Lal, B., & Agarwal, G. (2018). Effects of Brahma Kumaris Sahaj Raja Yoga Meditation on Health. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/493880a0a74fd324efdbc9327adac5ed6f98c617>
- [85]Learn Rajyoga Meditation, Brahma Kumaris, <https://www.brahmakumaris.com/rajyoga-meditation/>
- [86]Levine, G. N., Lange, R. A., Bairey-Merz, C. N., Davidson, R. J., Jamerson, K., Mehta, P. K., Michos, E. D., et al. (2017). Meditation and cardiovascular risk reduction: A scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Journal of the American Heart Association*, 6(10), e002218. <https://doi.org/10.1161/JAHA.117.002218>
- [87]Li, Y.-F., Sun, W., Sun, X.-J., Sun, J., Yang, D., Jia, B.-L., & Yuan, B.-Y. (2020). Effects of mindfulness meditation on anxiety, depression, stress, and mindfulness in nursing students: a meta-analysis and trial sequential analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Frontiers of Nursing*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/aa5fa504f22ff46934832dba0a7c365824ca0251>
- [88]M G, R.B., B, S., E., S., & S Rai, K. (2013). Efficacy of rajayoga meditation on positive thinking: an index for self-satisfaction and happiness in life. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research : JCDR*, 7 10, 2265-7 , [14b443f76c6f26abf470543b92401a7cfe51.pdf](https://www.ijirmf.com/wp-content/uploads/IJIRMF201708036.pdf)
- [89]Madhu, S., Govindaraj, R., Kumar, P., & Chandra, S. (2022). Stress and the impact of stressful events are lesser among raja yoga meditators – A cross sectional study during COVID-19 pandemic from India. *Clinical eHealth*, 5, 58 – 66, [Stress and the impact of stressful events are lesser among raja yoga meditators – A cross sectional study during COVID-19 pandemic from India - ScienceDirect](https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/clinical-ehealth)
- [90]Mahindroo, N., Srivastava, M., & Naik, V. (2022). Influence of Vipassana, Raja Yoga and Sudarshan Kriya Yoga on Well-being and Character strengths. *Purushartha - A Journal of Management Ethics and Spirituality*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/1a5b92b9bc0d081e920d256c2e4eb5708b7dc444>
- [91]Maini, S., Kaur, H., & Kohli, P.G. (2014). Effect of Rajayoga Meditation on Serum Cholesterol and HDL. *International Journal of Medical and Dental Sciences*, 3, 490-496.
- [92]Mallik, D., Bowen, S., Yang, Y., Perkins, R., & Sandoz, E. (2019). Raja yoga meditation and medication-assisted treatment for relapse prevention: A pilot study. *Journal of Substance Abuse Treatment*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/2e7b4dd581a5f65659a26b79a839fdbcdb1bb0edc>,
- [93]Mandape, A., Bharshankar, J.R., & Phatak, M.S. (2015). Effect of Raja Yoga Meditation on the Lipid Profile of Healthy Adults in Central India.

- [94] Manorama Year Book, UNGA declares December 21 as World Meditation Day, <https://www.manoramayearbook.in/current-affairs/world/2024/12/07/december-21-world-meditation-day.html>
- [95] Meditation and soul, <https://pdf-library.org/meditation-and-soul.pdf>
- [96] MEDITATION CH 6 - STEPS OF MEDITATION | SISTER JAYANTI, YOUTUBE, <HTTPS://WWW.YOUTUBE.COM/WATCH?V=TX9LOET5VBW>
- [97] Mehta, S., Mehta, K., Chalana, H., Singh, H., & Thaman, R. (2020). Effectiveness of Rajyoga meditation as an adjunct to first-line treatment in patients with obsessive compulsive disorder. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*. https://doi.org/10.4103/psychiatry.indianjpsychiatry_401_19
- [98] Misra, N., Gupta, A., Alreja, S., & Prakash, O. (2013). Effect of Raj Yoga meditation on affective and cognitive functions. *International Journal of Health Sciences & Research*, 3(2), 38–46. Retrieved from https://www.ijhsr.org/IJHSR_Vol.3_Issue.2_Feb2013/8.pdf
- [99] N. V. N., & Naragatti, S. (2023). Sacred Symbiosis: Cultivating Spiritual Mastery and Divine Innocence in the Wisdom of Brahma Kumaris. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 10(12), b811–b821. <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2312197.pdf>
- [100] N. V., N. (2023). Exploring Spiritual Growth and Well-Being: A Thematic Analysis of Rajayogini Brahma Kumari's (BK) Dadi Janki's Teachings, *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 10(11), e351–e360. <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2311447.pdf>
- [101] Nabilah, A., Azami, S., Dafhalla, A. K., Adibah, M. H., & Naimah, Y. (2021). The Effect of Meditation on Brain Relaxation Incorporating Different Physiological Activities. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/2755213e8d5b35a532e6acce4c66e2a41d8e8894>
- [102] Naemah, R. (2024). Soul healing through quantum consciousness. *Medium*. <https://medium.com/@naemahr/soul-healing-through-quantum-consciousness>
- [103] Nagesh, N. V. (2016) A Study of Motivational Factors to Learn Raja Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris International Head Quarters, Mount Abu, Jhunjunu, Rajasthan Shri Jagdishprasad Jhabarmal Tibrewala University Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/161475>
- [104] Nagesh, N. V. (2016) Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation (BKRM): A Study on Incumbent and Predominant Motivational Factors in Spiritual Enlightening Practices *Centum*, 9(2), 48–61.
- [105] Nagesh, N. V. (2016). A study of spiritual, physiological, and psychological factors motivating to learn Raja Yoga meditation of Brahma Kumaris. *CENTUM*, 9(2), 62–75, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371608103_Nagesh_-CENTUM-2
- [106] Nagesh, N. V. (2023). BrahmaKumaris RajYoga meditation in modern times: Addressing current issues and applications. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 10(6), b65–b77, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371416656_Brahma_kumaris_raja_yoga_meditation_in_modern_times_Addressing_the_current_issues_and_applications
- [107] Nagesh, N. V. (2023). Harmonising hearts and habitats: The symbiosis of Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga meditation and environmental consciousness. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 10(8), d697–d708. <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2308388.pdf>
- [108] Nagesh, N. V. (2023). Navigating the path to inner harmony: Lessons from the Mount Abu Brahma Kumaris community. *JETIR*, 10(6), k427–k435. Retrieved from <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2306A52.pdf>
- [109] Nagesh, N. V. (2023). Revitalising modern minds: Embracing Brahma Kumari's Raja Yoga meditation for modern challenges. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 10(7), 714–e736. Retrieved from <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2307477.pdf>
- [110] Nagesh, N. V. (2023). The transformational power of Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga meditation: Emerging trends and future perspectives. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 8(5), 554–563. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371416404_The_Transformative_Power_of_Brahma_Kumaris_Raja_Yoga_Meditation_Emerging_Trends_and_Future_Perspectives
- [111] Nagesh, N. V. (2023). Uncovering the mysteries of the RajYog meditation: A demographic analysis of Brahma Kumaris at Mount Abu. *International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field*, 9(5), 66–76. <https://www.ijirmf.com/wp-content/uploads/IJIRMF202305010-min.pdf>
- [112] Nagesh, N. V. (2023). Unveiling the motivations of Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga meditation practitioners at Mount Abu. *International Journal of Current Research*, 15(04), 24344–24348. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371416339_unveiling_the_motivations_of_brahma_kumaris_raja_yoga_meditation_practitioners_at_mount_abu
- [113] Nagesh, N. V., & Mehta, T. (2023). Impact of Rajyoga Meditation of Brahma Kumaris on Self-Regulation of Mind in Young Females. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 10(9), g86–g93. <http://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2309628.pdf>, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374380502_Impact_of_Rajyoga_Meditation_of_Brahma_Kumaris_on_Self-Regulation_Of_mind_on_young_females
- [114] Nagesh, N. V., & Naragatti, S. (2023). Empowering middle-aged women: Nurturing mental health through Brahma Kumaris Rajyoga. *International Journal of Family Medicine and Reproductive Health*, 5(4), 1–15, https://www.academia.edu/107473183/Empowering_Middle_aged_Women_Nurturing_Mental_Health_Through_Brahma_Kumaris_Rajyoga?uc-sb-sw=7353107

- [115] Nagesh, N. V., & Naragatti, S. (2023). Management of non-communicable diseases through Brahmakumaris Rajyoga. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 10(8), e402–409, <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2308449.pdf>
- [116] Nagesh, N. V., & Sachindra Babu, A. (2017). A study of motivational factors of Raja Yoga meditation at Brahma Kumaris, Mount Abu Headquarters. *CENTUM*, 9(3), 45–58, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371449947_A_Study_of_Motivational_Factors_to_Learn_Raja_Yoga_Meditation_at_Brahma_Kumaris_International_Head_Quarters_Mount_Abu_Rajasthan
- [117] Nagesh, N. V., & Sachindra Babu, A. (2017). Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga meditation effects on various health parameters. *CENTUM*, 9(3), 11–20, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371449305_brahma_kumaris_rajyoga_meditation_effects_on_various_health_parameters
- [118] Nagesh, N. V., & Sachindra Babu, A. (2017). Brahma Kumaris Rajyoga Meditation Effects on Various Health Parameters, *CENTUM*, 9(3), 11-20
- [119] Nagesh, N. V., & Tandel, B. (2024). Cognitive enhancements through Brahma Kumaris Rajayoga meditation: A comprehensive review. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 11(9), D471-D479. <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2409354.pdf>,
- [120] Nagesh, N.V. (2023). Discovering the Hidden Motivations of Raja Yoga Meditation at Brahma Kumaris World Headquarters, Mount Abu. *International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field*, 9(5), 206.-217, <https://www.ijirmf.com/wp-content/uploads/IJIRMF202305027-min.pdf>
- [121] Naragatti, S. (2019). Brahma Kumaris Sahaj Raj-Yoga Meditation - As a Tool to Manage Various Levels of Stress. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED RESEARCH IN AYURVEDA, YOGA, UNANI, SIDHHA & HOMEOPATHY*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/084ab45784dd44c3ac3b116ca5e7926d67d6718e>
- [122] Naragatti, S. (2020). Necessity and Significance of Meditation in Life. *JOURNAL OF ADVANCED RESEARCH IN AYURVEDA, YOGA, UNANI, SIDHHA & HOMEOPATHY*, [b6fe53b85c9a83255af671deaab426449692.pdf](https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/b6fe53b85c9a83255af671deaab426449692.pdf)
- [123] OSHO NEWS, UNITED NATIONS DECLARES DECEMBER 21 AS WORLD MEDITATION DAY, [HTTPS://WWW.OSHONWS.COM/2024/12/12/UNITED-NATIONS-DECLARES-DECEMBER-21-AS-WORLD-MEDITATION-DAY/](https://www.oshonews.com/2024/12/12/united-nations-declares-december-21-as-world-meditation-day/)
- [124] Pandya, S. (2018). Meditation for meaning in life and happiness of older adults: A multi-city experiment of the Brahma Kumaris' Raja yoga practice. *Journal of Religion, Spirituality & Aging*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/b15adc0199b0651d73dfb299dae69e92f9a38956>
- [125] Patra, S., Chatterjee, Dr. I., & Dasgupta, D. (2020). Impact of Pranayama, Hatha Yoga, and Raja Yoga Meditation on Executive Function and Metacognitive Regulation. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/4ce6a6ac61d54959f082768823d6cc4b80dd2181>
- [126] Phatak, M., Chawla, T. G., & Phatak, P. (2017). Effect of raja yoga meditation on glycaemic status in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/b990060cba97bf83d77d61b315859c1d34c1c62f>
- [127] Philosophy — Brahma Kumaris. (2024). Brahma Kumaris. <http://brahmakumarisresearch.org/philosophy>
- [128] Plato's theory of soul, In Wikipedia. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Plato%27s_theory_of_soul
- [129] Posted By: bkmilpitas. (2019). Connecting to the Supreme Charger. svbrahmakumaris.org/connecting-to-the-supreme-charger/
- [130] PURIFYING THE SOUL WITH RAJYOGA MEDITATION (2024), BRAHMA KUMARIS, [HTTPS://WWW.BRAHMAKUMARIS.COM/SOUL-SUSTENANCE/PURIFYING-THE-SOUL-WITH-RAJYOGA-MEDITATION/](https://www.brahmakumaris.com/soul-sustenance/purifying-the-soul-with-rajyoga-meditation/)
- [131] Rajoria, Kshipra & Sarvesh, Kumar & Singh, Sarvesh Kumar. (2017). Therapeutic benefits of Raj Yoga -A review. *Indian journal of traditional knowledge*. 16, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341130407_Therapeutic_benefits_of_Raj_Yoga_-A_review
- [132] Rajyoga Meditation- Brahma Kumaris, <https://bk.ooo/raja-yoga-meditation/>
- [133] Rajyoga Meditation: Journey Within Daily Life - Brahma Kumaris, <https://www.brahmakumaris.com/blog/rajyog-meditation/rajyoga-meditation-journey-within-daily-life/>
- [134] Ranzithkumar, N. (2023). The impact of Vipassana meditation on stress and anxiety: My clinical experience. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 11(2), 2733–2740. Retrieved from <https://ijip.in/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/18.01.264.20231102.pdf>
- [135] Rao, D. (2024). The Effects of Vipassana Meditation on Stress Reduction: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Indian Journal of Ayurveda & Alternative Medicines*, 1(1), 41–46., <https://jaam.shodhsagar.org/index.php/j/article/view/7>
- [136] Rastogi, S., Kumar, R., Hussain, M. S., & Rastogi, V. (2022). A comparative study to show the improvement in quality of life by short-term and long-term meditation by raj yoga meditation to reduce stress. *International Journal of Health Sciences*, 6(S7), 2033–2037.
- [137] Rastogi, S., Kumar, R., Hussain, M.S., & Rastogi, V. (2022). A comparative study to show the improvement in quality of life by short-term and long-term meditation by raj yoga meditation to reduce stress. *International journal of health sciences*, <https://doi.org/10.53730/ijhs.v6nS7.11747>
- [138] Reynolds, G. (2016). How meditation changes the brain and body. *The New York Times*. <https://archive.nytimes.com/well.blogs.nytimes.com/2016/02/18/contemplation-therapy/>

- [139] Rohatgi, P., & Singh, D. M. (2021). Emotional intelligence competencies developed through Raja Yoga meditation: A study of women in National Capital Region of India. *The Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 27(5), 791–804. Retrieved from <https://cibgp.com/au/index.php/1323-6903/article/view/2024>
- [140] SAHU, A.K., & DUBEY, D.S. (2016). RAJYOGA MEDITATION AND EFFECTS: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW, [HTTPS://RJWAVE.ORG/IJEDR/PAPERS/IJEDR1504174](https://RJWAVE.ORG/IJEDR/PAPERS/IJEDR1504174)
- [141] Saini, R., Upadhye, B. K. R., & Singh, D. (2024). Brahma Kumaris Raja Yoga Meditation and Hypertension: A Holistic Perspective. *Journal of Applied Consciousness Studies*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/1151952dd1af15e8143421c17aca6c955e5ba16d>
- [142] Sethuraman, K. (2018). A Comparative Study on Sky Yoga Meditation And Raja Yoga Meditation. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/260d2f4f03450f09d8134714f57bdd9317189c25>
- [143] Sharma, K., Achermann, P., Panwar, B., Sahoo, S., Angarai, R., Pascual-Marqui, R.D., & Faber, P.L. (2020). Brain-electric activity during eyes open Brahma Kumaris Rajayoga meditation, <https://doi.org/10.31231/osf.io/e48bv>
- [144] Silky Arora, & Garima Singh. (2023). Effectiveness of Brahma Kumaris Rajayoga Meditation on Quality of Life of Patients with Opioid Use Disorder. *Journal of Coastal Life Medicine*, 11(1), 1945–1951. Retrieved from <https://www.jclmm.com/index.php/journal/article/view/611>
- [145] Singh, Anjali. (2020). Rajyoga meditation and wellbeing status: An exploratory study, 10.24941/ijcr.33881.01.2019, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343485241_RAJYOGA_MEDITATION_AND_WELL_BEING_STATUS_AN_EXPLORATORY_STUDY
- [146] Singh, P. (2021). Emotional Intelligence Competencies Developed Through Raja Yoga Meditation: A Study of Women in National Capital Region of India. *The Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/5582f024206982830e07e5d3526cc4a92675fa47>
- [147] Singh, P. (2021). Emotional Intelligence Competencies Developed Through Raja Yoga Meditation: A Study of Women in National Capital Region of India. *The Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/5582f024206982830e07e5d3526cc4a92675fa47>
- [148] Singh, S. N., & Saxena, M. (2014). The Effect of ' Sahaj Marg Raja Yoga Meditation ' Practice on Mental Health *. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/ae47a5bb1e70f8670996dc76e471a2e5ddcee64f>
- [149] Sister Jayanti, *World Meditation Day*, <https://www.brahmakumaris.com/bktube/c/undefined/120130>
- [150] Siwach, A., & Sikka, S. (2024). The benefits of Rajyoga meditation for children and youth: A path to self-motivation and positive mindset. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 11(2), c125–c129. Retrieved from <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2402216.pdf>
- [151] Sonowal, A., & Doley, M. (2013). CONCEPT OF RAJA YOGA AND ITS PRACTICAL UTILITY. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/cd6e12188a455bd9f4414972832b8c54e10408d5>
- [152] Sukhshohale, N. D., Phatak, M. S., Sukhshohale, S. D., & Agrawal, S. B. (2012). Does Raja Yoga meditation bring out physiological and psychological general well-being among practitioners of it? *International Journal of Collaborative Research on Internal Medicine & Public Health*, 4(12), 2000–2012. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289961850_Does_Raja_Yoga_meditation_bring_out_physiological_and_psychological_general_well_being_among_practitioners_of_it
- [153] Sukhshohale, N., & Phatak, M. (2012). Effect of short-term and long-term Brahmakumaris Raja Yoga meditation on physiological variables. *Indian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/77d1202aa70fa681751d5942f1a913f784080a1a>
- [154] SukhshohaleNeelam, D., PhatakMrunal, S., SukhshohaleSachin, D., & AgrawalSanjay, B. (2012). Does Raja Yoga meditation bring out physiological andpsychological general well being among practitioners of it. *International Journal of Collaborative Research on Internal Medicine and Public Health*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/c70c651fb54349993f4186ac97615321adf76742>
- [155] Syamala, E., Roy, P., Sailesh, K., Jabir, P., Madhusudhan, U., & Jk, M. (2019). Effectiveness of Raja Yoga Meditation on Depression, Anxiety and Stress in Females with Premenstrual Syndrome. *International Journal of Physiology*. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/fd85895accddc63ff605e708c0f77459d32133bc>
- [156] Tandel, B., & N.V., N. (2023). The Impact of Brahma Kumaris Raj yoga Meditation on Anger Management Among Adolescents: A Critical Review *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research* (ISSN: 2349-5162), 10(10), b450-b458, <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2310143.pdf>
- [157] Tandel, B., & Nagesh, N. V. (2023). The impact of Brahma Kumaris Raj Yoga meditation on anger management among adolescents: A critical review. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*, 10(10), B450–B458, <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2310143.pdf>
- [158] Tang, Y.-Y., Hölzel, B. K., & Posner, M. I. (2015). The neuroscience of mindfulness meditation. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 16(4), 213–225. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn3916>
- [159] TEAM IDANIM, A COMPLETE GUIDE TO VIPASSANA MEDITATION AND ITS BENEFITS, [HTTPS://WWW.IDANIM.COM/BLOG/THE-BENEFITS-OF-VIPASSANA-MEDITATION-AND-HOW-TO-GET-STARTED](https://www.idanim.com/blog/the-benefits-of-vipassana-meditation-and-how-to-get-started)
- [160] Telles, S., & Desiraju, T. (1993). Autonomic changes in Brahmakumaris Raja yoga meditation. *International journal of psychophysiology : official journal of the International Organization of Psychophysiology*, 15 2, 147-52 , [Autonomic changes in Brahmakumaris Raja yoga meditation - PubMed](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10161111/)

- [161] THE HINDU, UNGA DECLARES DECEMBER 21 AS WORLD MEDITATION DAY, UNANIMOUSLY ADOPTS RESOLUTION CO-SPONSORED BY INDIA, [HTTPS://WWW.THEHINDU.COM/NEWS/INTERNATIONAL/UNGA-DECLARES-DECEMBER-21-AS-WORLD-MEDITATION-DAY-UNANIMOUSLY-ADOPTS-RESOLUTION-CO-SPONSORED-BY-INDIA/ARTICLE68957740.ECE](https://www.thehindu.com/news/international/unga-declares-december-21-as-world-meditation-day-unanimously-adopts-resolution-co-sponsored-by-india/article68957740.ece)
- [162] THE IMPACT OF MEDITATION ON THE SPIRITUAL WELL-BEING [HTTPS://WWW.RESEARCHGATE.NET/PUBLICATION/341694103_THE_IMPACT_OF_MEDITATION_ON_THE_SPIRITUAL_WELL-BEING](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341694103_the_impact_of_meditation_on_the_spiritual_well-being)
- [163] The Lighthouse. (2024). Who we are. The Lighthouse. https://thelighthouse.world/who_are_the_brahma_kumaris
- [164] THE ROLE OF MEDITATION: HOW DOES REGULAR MEDITATION PRACTICE IMPACT OUR SPIRITUAL JOURNEY?, TOI, [HTTPS://TIMESOFINDIA.INDIATIMES.COM/LIFE-STYLE/HEALTH-FITNESS/DE-STRESS/THE-ROLE-OF-MEDITATION-HOW-DOES-REGULAR-MEDITATION-PRACTICE-IMPACT-OUR-SPIRITUAL-JOURNEY/ARTICLESHOW/100853551.CMS](https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/life-style/health-fitness/de-stress/the-role-of-meditation-how-does-regular-meditation-practice-impact-our-spiritual-journey/articleshow/100853551.cms)
- [165] TOI, etimes. (2024, December 8). UN declares World Meditation Day on December 21: Here is the significance of the day for Indians. The Times of India. Retrieved from <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/life-style/health-fitness/health-news/un-declares-world-meditation-day-on-december-21-here-is-the-significance-of-the-day-for-indians/articleshow/116100228.cms>
- [166] TRANSCENDENTAL MEDITATION AND ITS MANY BENEFITS, [HTTPS://WWW.VERYWELLMIND.COM/TRANSCENDENTAL-MEDITATION-AND-ITS-MANY-BENEFITS-4159899](https://www.verywellmind.com/transcendental-meditation-and-its-many-benefits-4159899)
- [167] Transcendental meditation, <https://www.webmd.com/balance/transcendental-meditation-benefits-technique>
- [168] TRANSFORM KNOWLEDGE INTO WISDOM, [HTTPS://WWW.BRAHMAKUMARIS.COM/SOUL-SUSTENANCE/TRANSFORM-KNOWLEDGE-INTO-WISDOM/](https://www.brahmakumaris.com/soul-sustenance/transform-knowledge-into-wisdom/)
- [169] Transformation-1, BK Jagdish Bhai, You Tube, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FqMtokhQNi8>
- [170] Truhlar, L. M., Durand, C. R., Cooper, M. R., & Goldsmith, C.-A. W. (2022). Exploring the effects of a smartphone-based meditation app on stress, mindfulness, well-being, and resilience in pharmacy students. American Journal of Health-System Pharmacy : AJHP : Official Journal of the American Society of Health-System Pharmacists. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/38dc609e6b2024b9841cc9d5cd3c52112b751a34>
- [171] UN News page, One Link, <http://onelink.brahmakumaris.org/un-news-page>
- [172] Understanding God- Brahma Kumaris, <https://bk.ooo/understanding-god/>
- [173] United Nations, World Meditation Day, December 21, <https://www.un.org/en/observances/meditation-day>
- [174] Vyas, R., & Dikshit, N. (2002). Effect of meditation on respiratory system, cardiovascular system and lipid profile. Indian journal of physiology and pharmacology, 46(4), 487–491.
- [175] Wang, Y., Liao, L., Lin, X.-X., Sun, Y., Wang, N., Wang, J., & Luo, F. (2021). A Bibliometric and Visualization Analysis of Mindfulness and Meditation Research from 1900 to 2021. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/18/24/13150>
- [176] Website Admin. (2021). Our Relationship with God (the Supreme Soul). Brahma Kumaris. <https://www.shivbabas.org/post/our-relationship-with-god-the-supreme-soul>
- [177] What are the benefits of Rajyoga meditation taught by Brahma Kumaris? <https://www.quora.com/What-are-the-benefits-of-raja-yoga-meditation-taught-by-Brahma-Kumaris-Did-anyone-feel-its-benefits>
- [178] What does the Brahma Kumaris teach? (2024). Quora, <https://www.quora.com/What-does-the-Brahma-Kumaris-teach>
- [179] What is Meditation?, ISS Delhi, <https://issdelhi.org/meditation>
- [180] What is Raja yoga Meditation? <https://www.inspiredstillness.com/raja-yoga-meditation/>
- [181] What is Rajyoga Meditation? <https://www.brahmakumaris.org/meditation/raja-yoga-meditation>
- [182] What is Rajyoga? <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=844940786115854>
- [183] What is the concept of Brahma Kumaris? (2024). Quora, <https://www.quora.com/What-is-the-concept-of-Brahma-Kumaris>

13. AUTHOR BIOGRAPHY

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